

The effect of a support program based on the psychosocial needs of the family on the family care burden of ischemic heart patients: a systematic review study

El efecto de un programa de apoyo basado en las necesidades psicosociales de la familia sobre la carga de cuidado familiar de pacientes cardíacos isquémicos: un estudio de revisión sistemática

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Abstract

Introduction: Heart disease can have debilitating physical and mental consequences that can affect the care behavior of the elderly. The aim of study was the effect of a support program based on the psychosocial needs of the family on the family care burden of ischemic heart patients.

Methods: Science Direct, Pub Med, Google Scholar, SID, MagIran databases were reviewed and electronic data were used to identify the psychosocial needs of the family on the burden of family care of heart patients. In the initial search, 824 articles were obtained, of which 379 duplicate articles were removed. Considering the inclusion and exclusion criteria, the number of articles was reduced to 445 articles. Finally, 10 articles were included in study.

Results: A total of 824 articles were screened, which led to the selection of 11 studies that met the inclusion criteria and were included in study. Some studies defined caregivers as family caregivers. Five studies focused on life partners and caregivers of patients. Some studies generally defined caregivers as someone identified by the patient as a caregiver.

Conclusion: Providing a training program about the different dimensions of support that family caregivers need reduces the perceived stress of family caregivers of cardiac patients.

Keywords: support program, family psychosocial needs, care burden, family caregivers, ischemic heart disease.

Introducción y antecedentes. La enfermedad cardíaca puede tener consecuencias físicas y mentales debilitantes que pueden afectar el comportamiento de cuidado de los ancianos. El objetivo del estudio fue el efecto de un programa de apoyo basado en las necesidades psicosociales de la familia sobre la carga de cuidado familiar de los pacientes cardíacos isquémicos.

Métodos. Se revisaron las bases de datos Science Direct, Pub Med, Google Scholar, SID, MagIran y se utilizaron datos electrónicos para identificar las necesidades psicosociales de la familia en la carga del cuidado familiar de los pacientes cardíacos. En la búsqueda inicial, se obtuvieron 824 artículos, de los cuales se eliminaron 379 artículos duplicados. Teniendo en cuenta los criterios de inclusión y exclusión, el número de artículos se redujo a 445 artículos. Finalmente, se incluyeron 10 artículos en el estudio.

Resultados. Se examinaron un total de 824 artículos, lo que condujo a la selección de 11 estudios que cumplieron con los criterios de inclusión y se incluyeron en el estudio. Algunos estudios definieron a los cuidadores como cuidadores familiares. Cinco estudios se centraron en las parejas de vida y los cuidadores de los pacientes. Algunos estudios definieron en general a los cuidadores como alguien identificado por el paciente como cuidador.

Conclusión. Proporcionar un programa de capacitación sobre las diferentes dimensiones de apoyo que necesitan los cuidadores familiares reduce el estrés percibido por los cuidadores familiares de pacientes cardíacos.

Palabras clave: Programa de apoyo, necesidades psicosociales familiares, carga de cuidados, cuidadores familiares, cardiopatía isquémica.

Coronary heart disease is one of the biggest causes of death worldwide, leading to about 17.5 million deaths annually, 80% of which occur in low- and middle-income countries¹. Heart disease can have debilitating physical and mental consequences. Accordingly, patients often need significant care before, during, and immediately after surgery, and their long recovery period². However, patients with long-term and complex care needs are often cared for at home by family members thanks to technological advances and recent changes in the healthcare system that have shortened hospital stays³. Homecare services have increased family responsibility for providing patient care⁴.

Family caregivers care for patients with chronic diseases in various dimensions, including emotional and financial support during hospitalization periods, and physical and organizational tasks related to postoperative pain management, wound care, medication administration, and dietary and lifestyle changes⁵. These tasks increase the stress of the caregiver, which potentially threatens their health and causes chronic diseases⁶. Although the majority of care for cardiovascular patients is mostly the responsibility of family members, most studies have focused primarily on the needs of patients. A few studies assessed family caregiver burden, particularly in the Middle East^{7,8}. A previous qualitative study investigated the caregiver burden among family members of heart failure patients in Iran. Researchers identified four themes including lack of knowledge related to caregiving, physical exhaustion, psychosocial exhaustion, and lack of support, and emphasized the need to provide more effective social, informational, and professional support to family caregivers^{9,10}. This study investigated the effect of a support program based on the psychosocial needs of the family on the family care burden of ischemic heart patients in a systematic review.

The present study is a systematic review in which data were collected through searching for articles on the Internet. A systematic review answers precise clinical questions, and the evidence can be carefully reviewed and evaluated in topics where there is much data available with the help of systematic review. To obtain the required data, a search of Persian and English texts was conducted in the databases of Science Direct, Pub Med, Google Scholar, SID, and MagIran in the years 2000 to 2023. Articles were searched using the keywords of support program, family psychosocial needs, care burden, family caregivers, ischemic heart disease, and the English keywords including support program, family's psychosocial needs, care burden, family caregivers, and ischemic heart disease.

The inclusion criteria of the articles were articles published in reputable scientific journals, publication of the article in Persian or English, and access to the full text of the articles. In the search of articles, there were no limitations for the inclusion of studies based on the design of the conducted studies. The exclusion criteria included lack of access to the full text of the article, a letter to the editor, articles published in non-authoritative journals, and articles presented as posters at conferences.

In the initial search, 824 articles were obtained. Among them, 379 duplicate articles were removed. Given the inclusion and exclusion criteria, the number of articles was reduced to 445 articles. Among them, the articles related to the studied subject were screened and 121 studies were reviewed. To increase the strength of the research methodology, check the quality of the collected articles, and prevent possible biases, three researchers with a history of conducting systematic review articles reviewed the articles in terms of title, abstract, introduction, methodology, results, discussion, and references. Accordingly, their strengths and weaknesses were identified. Finally, 10 articles were included in the study Figure 1.

Our search approach, review methods, and reporting strategy conform to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines¹¹. Articles identified in our initial database search were screened for redundancy and duplicate articles were removed. Then, all remaining articles were reviewed for eligibility using the study title and abstract review by our study team. If articles were ineligible based on the information provided in the abstract, they were excluded from the sample. For the remaining studies, full-text articles were reviewed to determine eligibility.

If articles were ineligible according to the information provided in the abstract, they were excluded from the sample. For the remaining studies, full-text articles were reviewed to determine eligibility. Several members of

the research team screened the full-text article if it was unclear whether a full-text study should be included in the review sample. In this case, all decisions regarding inclusion/exclusion were shared with the entire team to ensure consistency. For studies that met our inclusion criteria, a table was created to report key study details, including study design, method, sample, variables/measures, primary results, identified psychosocial needs, and whether the study tested an intervention.

Figure 1. The process of selecting articles

Results

In this study, 824 articles were screened, leading to the selection of 10 studies that met the inclusion criteria and were included in our review Figure 1. Some studies defined caregivers as family caregivers. Five studies specifically focused on life partners and caregivers of patients. Some studies generally define a caregiver as someone identified by the patient as a caregiver. The results of the studies showed that the impact of care on the caregiver and the patient varies from physical and psychological to financial. Understanding the needs of caregivers to support the more complex medical care provided to patients with heart disease is vital and affects their recovery rate. A study found that overall burden and subscale scores were highest among caregivers caring for a close relative such as a parent, son/daughter, sibling, or spouse. The results of another study revealed that immediately after the intervention and one month after the intervention, the mean score of overall care burden and physical, emotional, social, developmental, and time domains in the control group was significantly higher than the experimental group, and the difference was significant between two groups Table 1.

Table 1. Characteristics of the studies, including the location and date of the study

Row	Subject	Authors	Location/time	Study type	N	The effect of the support program based on the psychosocial needs of the family on the family care burden of ischemic heart patients
1	Association of patient-reported psychosocial healthcare and risk of readmissions and mortality in patients with ischemic heart disease: A population-based cohort study	Zinckernagel et al. ¹²	Denmark/ 2022	Descriptive-analytical	1083	The risk of acute cardiac re-hospitalization was greater for patients reporting low psychosocial health care than for patients reporting high psychosocial health care. Acute cardiac re-hospitalization rates were 3.24 and 4.23 times higher among patients reporting low and moderate psychosocial health care, and re-hospitalization rates for any cause were 1.30 and 1.32 times higher. The risk of mortality was 2.86 and 2.88 times higher among patients who reported low and moderate psychosocial health care, respectively.
2	The COPE intervention for caregivers of patients with heart failure: an adapted intervention. Journal of Hospice & Palliative Nursing	McMillan et al. ¹³	State of Florida, USA/ 2013	Descriptive - cross-sectional	2000	The results revealed that the intervention had no effect, but the sample was small and the patients had been diagnosed for a mean of more than 10 years. The most common symptoms reported by patients were dry mouth and fatigue. Self-care was less than adequate, but depression and distress were low among patients, while quality of life scores were relatively high. Caregivers reported low distress from patient symptoms and caregiving burden and low mean anxiety and depression scores. We concluded that caregivers could manage heart failure symptoms for a long time and that our intervention is not needed near the end of the disease course. Caregivers already felt competent to manage the care of these patients.
3	American Heart Association Council on Cardiovascular and Stroke Nursing; Council on Quality of Care and Outcomes Research; Council on Clinical Cardiology; and Council on Lifestyle and Cardiometabolic Health	Kitko et al. ¹⁴	American Heart Association/ 2020	Mixed study	13 studies	The specific duties of caregivers of patients with heart disease are different based on the symptoms and co-morbidities of the patient, the relationship between the patient, and the caregiver, and the complexity of the treatment regimen. The effects of care on the caregiver and the patient vary from physical and psychological to financial. Thus, it is crucial to understand the needs of caregivers to support the more complex medical care they provide to cardiac patients. This scientific statement synthesizes the evidence from the care of adults with heart disease to define the role of heart care and how it changes with the course of the disease.
4	Effect of an Educational Support Programme on Caregiver Burden Among the Family Members of Patients Undergoing Coronary Artery Bypass Graft Surgery	Dalirirad et al. ¹⁵	Iran/ 2021	Non-randomized controlled clinical trial	80	Significant difference between family caregivers in the control and intervention groups before or after it according to the differences in the mean CBI scores (+67.1± 23.19 vs. +17.45 ± 9.83), with an effect size of -1.14 was observed. Also, the mean IADL scores after discharge in CABG patients in the intervention group increased significantly compared to the control group.
5	Assessment of the burden on caregivers of patients with mental disorders in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia	Alzahrani et al. ¹⁶	Saudi Arabia/ 2017	Cross-sectional	377	The mean total IEQ burden score of caregivers was 38.4. "Stress" was significantly more significant among young caregivers aged ≤30 years. "Worry" was significantly higher among caregivers living with their spouses and children and in families with relatively fewer members (6 members). "Insistence" was significantly higher among caregivers living in the same household as the patient and those who had been in close contact with the patient for 28 days in the four weeks before the study. Similarly, "insistence" was significantly higher among caregivers who cared for mentally ill women and those who did not receive any type of professional support. Total burden and subscale scores were highest among caregivers caring for a close relative such as a parent, son/daughter, sibling, or spouse.
6	Investigating the effect of family-focused nursing intervention on caregiver burden of the family members of the patients undergoing coronary bypass surgery in Isfahan Shahid Chamran Hospital during 2012	Moieni et al. ¹⁷	Isfahan/ 2014	Clinical trial	50	The mean and SD of the care burden before and after the intervention were 30.08 (14.03) and 19.2 (10), respectively, and in the control group, they were 30.16 (12.62) and 35.44 (10.42). Changes in the total care burden scores after the intervention in the study and control groups showed a significant difference. The score changes of subscales of time dependence, developmental, physical, and emotional care burden were also significant.
7	Family care and subjective well-being of coronary heart disease patients after percutaneous coronary intervention: Mediating effects of coping strategies	Liang et al. ¹⁸	China/ 2021	Descriptive-analytical	242	The mean scores of family care, exposure, avoidance, acceptance-withdrawal, and well-being of the subjects were 7.59 ± 2.24, 20.03 ± 3.78, 16.49 ± 2.70, and 10.42 ± 2.01, and 73.31 ± 3.11, respectively. Subgroup analysis showed that the path coefficient between family care and mental well-being was higher in males than in females. Family caregiving was directly associated with coping strategies. Coping strategies were directly associated with both of them, while family care showed an indirect relationship with coping strategies.
8	Analysis of the effects of a support program based on psychosocial needs of families on care burdens of family caregivers of patients with ischemic heart disease hospitalized in Chamran heart ward of Isfahan University of Medical Sciences.	Shariati Far et al. ¹⁹	Isfahan/ 2016	Clinical trial	64	In the control group, there was a significant difference between the mean scores of care burden in three times. Apart from the physical domain, no significant difference was observed between the control groups. The results showed that immediately after the intervention and one month after the intervention, the mean score of overall care burden and domains (physical, emotional, social, developmental, and time) in the control group was significantly higher than the experimental group and there was a significant difference between the two groups. The results also revealed no significant difference between the two experimental and control groups in the mean overall care burden and domains (physical, emotional, social, developmental, and time) of caregivers of ischemic heart patients before the intervention.
9	Influence of caregiving on lifestyle and psychosocial risk factors among family members of patients hospitalized with cardiovascular disease	Aggarwal et al. ²⁰	Columbia University/2009	Descriptive-analytical	263	The prevalence of serving as the primary caregiver of a CVD patient or caring for the patient most of the time was 50% at 6 months. Caregivers (primary) were more likely to be female (81% vs. 19%), married/living with someone, older than 50 years, with ≤ high school education, unemployed, less physically active, and with higher waist circumference. In the multivariate-adjusted model, mean scores of caregiver pressure were significantly higher among individuals with depression symptoms and low social support.
10	Supporting families in the ICU: a descriptive correlational study of informational support, anxiety, and satisfaction with care	Bailey et al. ²¹	Quebec/ Canada/ 2010	Analytical-correlational	29 families	The results are related to the ultimate goals of modifying a local information support plan and its final evaluation, and in doing so, they are of greater interest to others attempting to make evidence-based improvements in care for similar populations.

Given the importance of caring for cardiovascular patients to maintain recovery and promote individual health, this systematic review investigates the impact of a support program based on the psychosocial needs of the family on the family care burden of patients with ischemic heart disease. Nurses spend much time with patients and their families, so it is crucial to examine the burden of caregivers and provide appropriate interventions for them. One of the vital tasks of nurses is to discover the needs and concerns of family members during hospitalization and stay in the hospital²². Family members of patients are at the center of attention in nursing care for several reasons. It is believed that family-centered nursing care can be effective on the patient's burden tolerance. The attention and care of patients with ischemic heart disease should expand to the whole family²³.

Nurses' view of patients' family members is a crucial component in the recovery process of patients. Physical and psychological support for the patient and his family members is one of the approaches to providing patient-centered care²⁴. Family-centered care based on psychological and social needs is supported by associations such as the Health Care Association, Nursing Care Standards, Professional Care Association, and Special Care Association²⁵. Although one of the basic components of care is the interaction and proper communication between the family and the treatment team in the hospital, the contact between the care team and the family in the hospital is minimal. Nurses are in a good position to meet the needs of the family, but they allocate little time for it²⁶ and the burden of the caregiver often remains unknown²⁷.

Studies have indicated that families need help for continuous adaptation and their biggest need is the need for education and support. However, studies have reported that modern hospital technology does not pay attention to the issue of supporting families and families do not have enough support²⁶. In this regard, studies indicate that most nurses spend the least possible time communicating with patients' families²⁸. A study by Loqmani et al., also showed that patients' caregivers are ignored by the center's personnel and they face continuous stress in the environment due to the conflict between the lack of sufficient knowledge in care and the mandatory care of their patients²⁶.

Caregivers often need extensive support in physical, psychological, spiritual, and emotional aspects. However, most cases are related to the physical aspect and the psychological and social aspects are ignored. Educational, supportive, and psychotherapy interventions significantly reduce the caregiver burden²⁷. Interventions

and support measures for caregivers are among the effective interventions in reducing the burden of caregivers, as mentioned in many articles and studies. In interventions based on psychosocial support, information about the patient's disease process is provided, and the necessary training is provided to help the caregiver respond appropriately to the problems that arise for the patient regarding the disease, such as anxiety, anger, depression, pain, fatigue, sleep disorder, and appetite disorder. Self-care is also taught to caregivers. Among other measures mentioned in the studies regarding the burden of caregiving are supportive interventions including talking with the caregiver, allowing discussion of the difficulties and problems, individual successes in caring for the patient, teaching problem-solving methods and skills, and the way of using them can affect the level of psychosocial needs²⁹.

Unlike the extensive studies conducted on identifying the needs of family members, few studies have been conducted to meet these needs. Studies indicate that the needs are often left unanswered, while family support reduces adverse psychological effects and increases the patient's adaptation to disease³⁰. Prioritizing the needs of the family caregivers of the patients based on the needs assessment questionnaire is vital. Since the nurse's point of view in prioritizing the needs of the family caregivers may be different from that of the family caregivers and the focus of attention of nursing actions should be the patient and his family, assessing the needs of caregivers will be very effective to support them³¹.

The vital role of the family in caring for the patient has been known. The pressure and burden on the caregiver and the patient's family in the case of neurological diseases such as dementia, schizophrenia, cancer, hemodialysis, etc. have been extensively investigated. However, interventional studies on the burden of caregivers of ischemic heart patients are limited. Family is the most crucial human support system and family members play a vital role in caring for people, and this role continues even when the person is hospitalized. Thus, the caregivers should be supported by the formal system given the family's support role in the support of people and its impact on the more effective services of formal care systems.

Providing a training program on the different dimensions of support that family caregivers need reduces the perceived stress of family caregivers of cardiac patients. Thus, it is recommended to implement this intervention in this group of caregivers. Providing a psychosocial support program can reduce perceived stress in family caregivers of heart patients.

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